

1 Title:

2 **High-power optical photovoltaic transmission: towards a new paradigm**

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16
17 Abstract:

18 High-power optical transmission (HPOT) holds transformative potential for revolutionizing
19 energy delivery, offering a groundbreaking leap forward in how power is supplied and accessed.
20 By utilizing a monochromatic light source as emitter and an optical photovoltaic converter as
21 receiver, HPOT systems enable the sustainable transfer of kilowatts of power over hundreds of
22 kilometers, overcoming the limitations of conventional copper wiring. This technology unlocks
23 an extensive range of applications, from underwater environments to outer space, while driving
24 disruptive advances in strategic fields such as energy supply, defense, communications, and
25 healthcare. This work provides a comprehensive review of HPOT systems, including both optical
26 wireless power transmissions and power-over-fiber systems. It begins with a historical overview
27 and a description of the key performance indicators of the technology, followed by an evaluation
28 of suitable high-power light sources. Then, the physical phenomena affecting light propagation
29 are examined, as well as tracking mechanisms and safety measures that must be considered. Next,
30 the photovoltaic receiver is analyzed in terms of intrinsic and extrinsic losses, and a
31 comprehensive compilation of state-of-the-art performance results is presented. Finally, terrestrial
32 and space prospective applications are explored, along with a survey of HPOT demonstrations
33 conducted to date. Through a detailed research of the advantages, challenges, and key
34 achievements of HPOT technology, this review aims to provide valuable insights to accelerate its
35 development and adoption, paving the way for a more connected and sustainable future.

36
37 Keywords:

38 energy efficient usage, clean energy, high power optical transmission, optical wireless power
39 transmission, power over fiber, light propagation, optical photovoltaic converters

40
41 **Glossary**

42 *Nomenclature*

43 c - Speed of light, m s^{-1}

44 C_n^2 - Refractive-index structure parameter, $\text{m}^{-2/3}$

45 d - Distance, m

46 E_g - Energy gap, eV

47 EQE - External quantum efficiency, %

48 FF - Fill factor, %

49 h - Planck constant, $\text{m}^2\text{kg s}^{-1}$

50 I - Electrical current, A

51 I_p - Peak intensity, W

- 1 L_{ij} - Additional losses
- 2 M^2 - Beam quality factor, dimensionless
- 3 n - refractive index, dimensionless
- 4 P_{in} - Input power, W
- 5 P_{out} - Output power, W
- 6 P_S - Light source power, W
- 7 RL - Radiative efficiency limit, %
- 8 R_S - Series resistance, Ωcm^{-2}
- 9 T - Temperature, K
- 10 T_C - Temperature coefficient, $\% \text{K}^{-1}$
- 11 v_{\perp} - Transverse fluid velocity, m s^{-1}
- 12 V_{mpp} - Voltage at the maximum power point, V
- 13 V_{OC} - Open-circuit voltage, V
- 14
- 15 *Greek symbols*
- 16 α - Absorption coefficient, m^{-1}
- 17 β - Scattering coefficient, m^{-1}
- 18 η_{E-E} - End-to-end efficiency, %
- 19 η_{E-O} - Electrical-to-optical efficiency, %
- 20 η_{O-E} - Optical-to-electrical efficiency, %
- 21 η_{PV} - Photovoltaic efficiency, %
- 22 η_S - Light source efficiency, %
- 23 η_T - Transmission efficiency, %
- 24 Θ_D - Divergence due to diffraction, mrad
- 25 Θ_J - Divergence due to mechanical jitter, mrad
- 26 Θ_L - Divergence due to linear effects, mrad
- 27 Θ_Q - Divergence due to beam quality
- 28 Θ_S - Divergence or angular spread, mrad or degrees
- 29 Θ_T - Divergence due to turbulence, mrad
- 30 Θ_{TB} - Divergence due to thermal blooming, mrad
- 31 λ - Wavelength, nm
- 32 ρ_{in} - Input power density, Wcm^{-2}
- 33 τ - Extinction coefficient, m^{-1}
- 34
- 35 *Abbreviations*
- 36 AEL - Accessible Emission Limit
- 37 ANSI - American National Standards Institute
- 38 AUV - Autonomous underwater vehicle
- 39 CPV - Concentrator photovoltaics
- 40 CW - Continuous-wave
- 41 DCCPC - Dielectric-cross compound-parabolic-concentrator
- 42 DPAL - Diode-pumped alkali laser
- 43 DPSSL - Diode-pumped solid-state laser
- 44 ESA - European Space Agency
- 45 HPOT - High-power optical transmission
- 46 ICNIRP - International Commission on Non-Ionizing Radiation Protection
- 47 IEC - International Electrotechnical Commission
- 48 LD - Laser diode
- 49 LPC - Laser power converter
- 50 MJ - Multi-junction
- 51 MPE - Maximum Permissible Exposure

- 1 mrad - milliradian
- 2 NASA - National Aeronautics and Space Agency
- 3 NOHD - Nominal Ocular Hazard Distance
- 4 OPC - Optical photovoltaic converter
- 5 OWPT - Optical wireless power transmission
- 6 PCSEL - Photonic-crystal surface-emitting laser
- 7 PoF - Power-over-fiber
- 8 PPC - Photonic power converter
- 9 PV - Photovoltaic
- 10 PVLPC - Photovoltaic laser power converter
- 11 RTP - Refractive truncated pyramid
- 12 RL - Radiative limit
- 13 SBS - Stimulated Brillouin scattering
- 14 SBSP - Space-based solar power
- 15 SCL- Semiconductor laser
- 16 SILO - Single-lens-optical element
- 17 SPM - Self-phase modulation
- 18 SRS - Stimulated Raman scattering
- 19 SSL - Solid-state laser
- 20 UAV - Unmanned aerial vehicle
- 21 VCSEL - Vertical-cavity surface emitting laser
- 22 VECSEL - Vertical external-cavity surface emitting laser
- 23 WPT - Wireless power transmission
- 24 XPM - Cross-phase modulation

25

26 **1. Introduction**

27 Providing immediate, reliable energy anytime, anywhere is a challenge far from being trivial.
28 Limited storage capacity, the absence of nearby power grids, environmental hazards, and physical
29 constraints in conventional power delivery methods have historically made this issue particularly
30 complex to resolve [1]. It is in these situations where high-power optical transmissions (HPOT)
31 excel. Often referred to as power beaming or power-by-light [2], this technology consists in a
32 monochromatic light source that transfers energy via optical beams to a photovoltaic (PV)
33 receiver. By eliminating the constraints of traditional electrical cables, HPOT enables the
34 transmission of kilowatts of power over distances in the order of tens of kilometers, or even
35 further, and it also supplies energy in environments where traditional wires are problematic or
36 impossible to use safely. In this sense, optical energy transmission provides unique advantages
37 compared to electrical methods, such as operational flexibility, galvanic insulation, immunity to
38 electromagnetic interference, elimination of electric sparks risks, weight reduction due to
39 minimized cabling and energy storage, and the ability to simultaneously transfer both power and
40 data [3–6]

41 In general, two main approaches within HPOT can be identified: optical wireless power
42 transmissions (OWPT) [7], which are strictly cable-free, and transmissions through optical fibers,
43 usually called power-over-fiber (PoF) [2,8]. Regarding the former, OWPT has been considered
44 an expensive and inefficient alternative to existing technologies until recently [1], when these
45 drawbacks have been progressively mitigated thanks to intensive research and development
46 efforts, which has already provided a commercial-scale production and widespread adoption
47 across industries of its key components.[1]. While efficiency improvements remain indeed
48 necessary [9], that does not prevent the technology from enabling a vast variety of applications
49 across both spatial and terrestrial (atmospheric and underwater) domains, with potential impact
50 across multiple fields such as energy transmission, communications, defense, and even healthcare
51 [10–13]. Optical transmissions offer versatile remote powering capabilities ranging from small

1 devices such as sensors and pacemakers, medium-size targets and vehicles like robots, rovers,
2 and aircrafts, and extending to large-scale infrastructures, including uninterrupted energy supply
3 from virtual space grids, such as space- and moon-based solar power stations [14–26]. This has
4 positioned OWPT as one of the most promising far-field wireless power transmission (WPT)
5 technologies [4], contributing to the remarkable growth of the wireless transmission market,
6 valued at \$13.3 billion in 2023 and projected to reach \$37.7 billion by 2032 [27]. This growth is
7 further evidenced by the recent emergence of numerous OWPT-based companies, which will be
8 commented later.

9 Moreover, OWPT exhibits several benefits over alternative far-field wireless technologies,
10 particularly microwaves, including reduced spreading, superior directionality, lower
11 susceptibility to electromagnetic interference, longer transmission distances, and greater
12 compactness and portability [12]. These characteristics result in more concentrated energy
13 (reducing transmission times), smaller receiver apertures, enhanced equipment relocation
14 mobility, lower cost per unit mass, and improved data protection security. However, microwaves
15 have their own advantages, such as higher power capabilities, better resistance to weather
16 conditions, and potentially slightly better system performance [3,14,28–31]. Ultimately, the
17 choice between the two technologies depends on specific environmental conditions and
18 application requirements.

19 On the other hand, fiber optics are becoming increasingly popular [8]. When compared to
20 traditional copper wires, they offer significant advantages: lighter weight, smaller size, and
21 insulation against galvanic contacts and electromagnetic noise [6]. These attributes make fiber
22 optics an ideal solution for applications in confined spaces and high-risk environments, such as
23 exclusion zones in refineries, mines, fuel tanks, and nuclear power plants, where the risk of fire
24 or explosion is significant [2]. Additionally, optical fibers facilitate reliable, fast, and secure data
25 transmission, making them particularly well-suited for hazardous settings and aircrafts navigation
26 systems, for example [32,33]. In summary, HPOT systems offer extensive potential applications,
27 with many possibilities yet to be explored.

28 This work aims to provide a comprehensive review of HPOT systems, presenting high-power
29 OWPT while also addressing PoF. To provide some context, the review begins with a brief history
30 and description of the technology, highlighting its key performance indicators. Next, potential
31 high-power light source options are examined, outlining the properties that they should exhibit
32 and the suitable types currently available or expected in the near future. The paper then describes
33 the phenomena affecting optical energy propagation, including attenuation, turbulence, thermal
34 blooming, beam divergence, peak intensity variation, and other effects related to propagation via
35 optical fibers, as well as tracking mechanisms and safety measures. After that, the PV receiver,
36 or optical photovoltaic converter (OPC), is described and analyzed in terms of both its intrinsic
37 and extrinsic losses. Additionally, an extensive compilation of reported results is presented,
38 comparing the efficiencies and power outputs achieved. To conclude, the terrestrial and space
39 applications of HPOT systems are explored, and a survey of publicly available HPOT trials is
40 presented, examining the current limitations that faces this technology in various environmental
41 contexts. Our intention is to provide an in-depth overview of this technology, with insights into
42 its advantages, areas of improvement, and important achievements to date.

43 **2. History, description and key performance indicators of the technology**

44 The foundations of HPOT technology were laid several decades ago, dating back to the late 1960s.
45 Peter Glaser, a prominent reference figure in the field, along with the National Aeronautics and
46 Space Agency (NASA), were the first to attempt to realize Isaac Asimov’s futuristic concept of
47 wireless power transfer in space, originally presented in 1941 in his science fiction story “Reason”
48 [34]. While Glaser focused solely on microwave technology [35], NASA also explored optical
49 sources, such as lasers, as an alternative way to transmit high powers. In their first reports and up
50

1 until the 2000s, NASA studied the feasibility of OWPT, mainly for space applications [25,36–
2 41].

3 In parallel, during the late 1970s, another branch of HPOT, known as PoF, started to take shape
4 [42]. PoF differentiated itself by removing the wireless feature of HPOT systems, instead
5 transmitting power through optical fibers rather than through an open medium, such as space, air,
6 or water [8]. Far from being a disadvantage, PoF systems are well-suited to different but equally
7 relevant applications, which will be further discussed in section 6.

8 Despite its relatively long history, HPOT (encompasses both OWPT and PoF systems) has only
9 recently gained significant momentum and has been successfully applied across a wide range of
10 settings [1,2,7,8]. Evidence of the growing interest in this topic can be seen in academic research,
11 as illustrated in Fig. 1, where the number of publications and congresses has shown a noticeable
12 surge over the past decade. Moreover, not only reputed research centers, universities, and
13 government agencies have contributed to the field, such as the Fraunhofer Institute for Solar
14 Energy (Germany), Advances in Photovoltaic Technology-University of Jaén and Solar Energy
15 Institute-Technical University of Madrid (Spain), University of Ottawa and University of
16 Sherbrooke (Canada), Tokyo Institute of Technology and Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency
17 (Japan), Ioffe Institute of St. Petersburg (Russia), NASA and National Renewable Energy
18 Laboratory (USA), and the European Space Agency (ESA), to cite some, but also the private
19 sector is committed to exploit the potential of this technology; several startups, such as
20 PowerLight Technologies, Aquila, Volta Space Technologies, ORiS, SunCubes, and SkyGrids,
21 have recently burst into the power beaming market, joining more established companies, like JDS
22 Uniphase Corporation, AzurSpace, Broadcom, and Spectrolab, among others. As can be seen, the
23 industrial ecosystem around HPOT systems is growing fast and the future looks bright.

25
26 Fig. 1. Number of publications in relation to the HPOT topic [43].

27
28 The operation of HPOT systems involves delivering substantial energy to a remote device using
29 a monochromatic (or quasi-monochromatic) light source. These systems are generally divided
30 into two main sub-systems: the emitter and the receiver, as illustrated in Fig. 2 [2]. The emitter
31 system includes a source that generates monochromatic light and ensures high-quality beam
32 emission in terms of collimation, uniformity, and directionality, e.g. lasers. This requires
33 equipment such as beam shaping and steering optics, a beam director, and power management
34 and distribution electronics, which handle critical functions like thermal management, telemetry,
35 safety, and tracking. The receiver system, in turn, consists of components that convert the
36 transferred optical energy into electrical energy. The key component of this system is the PV
37 receiver, referred to by various names, including optical photovoltaic converter (OPC), photonic
38 power converter (PPC), photovoltaic laser power converter (PVLPC), or laser power converter
39 (LPC), among others. For consistency, we will use the term OPC hereafter. Additionally, the
40 receiver incorporates optics and control electronics similar to those used in the emitter system.

1 Regarding the transmission medium, the optical power can be transmitted either wirelessly
 2 through atmosphere, water, or vacuum (outer space), or via optical fiber cables. In all cases,
 3 traditional copper wiring is not involved in the transmission process.

4

5

6 Fig. 2. Diagram of HPOT systems, illustrating the emitter and receiver sub-systems, from input
 7 to output power. The beam control unit consists of beam shaping and steering optics, as well as
 8 the beam director. The control electronics are the components that handle management and
 9 distribution tasks, including monitoring thermal sensors, telemetry, safety, and tracking
 10 equipment.

11

12 To evaluate HPOT systems, various indicators can be defined to quantify their performance and
 13 capabilities. Numerous parameters have been proposed, focusing on several aspects such as
 14 power, mass, area, volume, wavelength, time, and efficiencies across different parts of the system
 15 [1,44]. The most representative indicators from a general perspective are summarized in Table 1,
 16 and will be further discussed throughout the article.

17

18 Table 1. Key performance indicators of HPOT systems.

Indicator	Description
Electrical-to-optical efficiency (η_{E-O})	Efficiency of the emitter system. Calculated as $\eta_{E-O} = \eta_S (1-L_i)$, where η_S is the efficiency of the light source, e.g. laser, and L_i accounts for the i -additional losses such as the optical losses from the optical emitting system, and the fraction of energy consumed by auxiliary components, including beam control electronics, sensors, wiring, tracking equipment, and other supporting elements. Units: %.
Transmission efficiency (η_T)	Ratio of input power at the receiver system to the output power from the emitter system. Units: %.
Optical-to-electrical efficiency (η_{O-E})	Efficiency of the receiver system. Calculated as $\eta_{O-E} = \eta_{PV} (1-L_j)$, where η_{PV} is the PV efficiency of the OPCs, and L_j represents the j -additional losses such as the fraction of energy used by the control electronics and energy losses due to current mismatches among the electrical connection of several OPCs with an inherent electrical tolerance, optical losses from the optical receiving system to eventually spread and/or focused the light on the OPCs, and also due to light spillage, wiring, etc. Units: %.
End-to-end efficiency (η_{E-E})	Overall system performance, calculated as the ratio of final output power to initial input power, or $\eta_{E-E} = \eta_{E-O} \times \eta_T \times \eta_{O-E}$. Units: %.
Power (P_S)	Optical power supplied by the light source. Units: W or kW. Alternative, it is sometimes given as power density: Wcm^{-2} .
Distance (d)	Spatial separation between the emitter and receiver systems. Units: m or km.
Divergence (θ_S)	Angular spread of a beam as it propagates from the light source. It determines how far a beam can be effectively focused. Units: milliradians (mrad) or degrees.

1 These parameters provide a consistent basis for comparing not only HPOT systems but also
2 extending to WPT systems, enabling the rapid identification of the most suitable configurations
3 for the specific applications. Furthermore, they help pinpoint the components that most adversely
4 affect overall performance and require attention. For instance, both electrical-to-optical and
5 photovoltaic efficiencies are the areas where efficiency degradation is most significant, and
6 further technological advancements are necessary to achieve more desirable system efficiencies
7 [4].

9 **3. Light source**

10 As commented in the previous section, the emitter is a critical component of HPOT systems and
11 one of the primary factors limiting the overall performance of the technology. Hence, selecting
12 an appropriate light source is essential for high end-to-end efficiency (η_{E-E}). To accomplish this,
13 the light source should exhibit the following characteristics [2,4,45]: (a) suitable wavelength (λ)
14 for both PV conversion and light propagation; (b) high light source efficiency (η_s), enough power
15 (ranging from watts to kilowatts depending on the application requirements), and continuous-
16 wave (CW) mode operation is preferable over pulsed modes; (c) small beam divergence; and (d)
17 good directionality and reliability.

18 Furthermore, it is advisable that the optical source demonstrates compactness, low weight-to-
19 power ratio, low-cost, acceptable thermal management (avoid large cooling equipment,
20 particularly in applications in which size and weight play a crucial role), long lifespan, stability,
21 and, ideally, powered by sustainable sources. Bearing the above in mind, lasers emerge as clear
22 candidates, as they can potentially fulfil all the aforementioned requirements [2,4,46–48].

23 Laser light possesses unique characteristics that distinguish it from other light sources:
24 monochromaticity, coherence (temporal and spatial) and directionality [49]. These properties
25 result in high radiance (also known as brightness, as it quantifies the power emitted per unit area
26 per unit solid angle, measured in $\text{Wm}^{-2}\text{sr}^{-1}$), high spectral purity, variable repetition rate (from
27 pulse to continuous wave), and excellent modulation control, making lasers ideal for high-power
28 applications [45]. This section identifies the most suitable lasers for HPOT according to the
29 aforementioned must-have characteristics.

30 - *Semiconductor lasers* (SCLs). SCLs use a semiconductor material as the active medium,
31 achieving optical gain through stimulated emission from inter-band transitions at high carrier
32 densities. Although technically solid-state devices, they are often classified separately due to their
33 unique population inversion mechanisms [49]. The most common SCLs are *laser diodes* (LDs),
34 electrically-pumped edge-emitting semiconductor lasers known for their high efficiency (~50%),
35 compactness, acceptable cooling requirements, cost-effectiveness, and great modularity, as they
36 are often stacked in arrays to increase output power [45–47,49]. LDs emit across a broad
37 wavelength range, making them compatible with most PV materials. High-power LDs (up to 45
38 kW) are commercially available (e.g. QPC Laser, AeroDiode, Laserline [50–52]), but their low
39 radiance requires advanced optical systems for compensation. Techniques like spectral beam
40 combining can mitigate this limitation, but the achievable power level is considerably lower. Still,
41 LDs are suitable for short-range power beaming (tens of kilometers) [46].

42 In addition to LDs, surface-emitting lasers such as *vertical-cavity surface-emitting lasers*
43 (VCSELs) offer another approach. VCSELs emit light perpendicular to the wafer surface,
44 enabling compact designs but with limited power output. To address this, *vertical external-cavity*
45 *surface-emitting lasers* (VECSELs) incorporate external mirrors, improving power and beam
46 quality and making them more suitable for high-power applications [49].

47 Despite the advantages of SCLs, their brightness remains a concern for its utilization in certain
48 applications as the maximum values are around $100 \text{ MWcm}^{-2}\text{sr}^{-1}$ [53]. This has driven the
49 development of *photonic-crystal surface-emitting lasers* (PCSELs), which incorporate a 2D
50 photonic crystal to enhance performance. PCSELs achieve high single-mode coherent power, low

1 divergence, beam steering, polarization control, and superior beam quality [54–62]. Recent
 2 advancements include 50 W PCSELS achieving $1 \text{ GWcm}^{-2}\text{sr}^{-1}$ [63], with future goals targeting ~ 1
 3 $\text{TWcm}^{-2}\text{sr}^{-1}$ brightness, $\sim 10 \text{ kW}$ power, and $\sim 60\%$ efficiency [53].

4 - *Diode-pumped solid-state lasers* (DPSSLs). DPSSLs are solid-state lasers optically
 5 pumped by LDs, ensuring a precise spectral overlap of the pump emission with the absorption
 6 band of the gain medium. While traditional optical excitation methods relied on lamp pumping or
 7 other laser types, LDs provide superior performance [64]. Their solid-state gain medium consists
 8 of crystals, glasses, or ceramics doped with rare earth or transition metal ions DPSSLs offer
 9 compact design, long lifespan, high efficiency, good and stable beam quality, and exceptionally
 10 high output power. The emission wavelengths span from 0.7 to $3 \mu\text{m}$, although shorter values can
 11 be achieved in non-linear materials by frequency doubling methods [65–68].

12 Among solid-state lasers (SSLs), *fiber lasers* are particularly notable. They use rare earth doped
 13 fibers as active medium. Compared to bulk SSLs, fiber lasers exhibit higher efficiencies (up to
 14 50% versus $\sim 30\%$ for bulk lasers, in exchange of requiring improved pumping LD), and a superior
 15 beam quality at more intense light output powers. They are robust, stable, and commercially
 16 available at 120 kW CW with $>40\% \eta_s$ (e.g. IPG Photonics [69]), making them a strong candidate
 17 for HPOT [49,70].

18 *Disk lasers*, another DPSSL variant, are characterized by a thin, circular shape. They deliver high
 19 power with acceptable beam quality (up to 24 kW CW [71]) and offer enhanced design flexibility
 20 and modularity for power scaling compared to fiber lasers [72,73], presenting a viable alternative
 21 for HPOT applications.

22 - *Diode-Pumped Alkali Lasers* (DPALs). DPALs are a recently developed class of gas
 23 lasers that use atomic alkali vapors as gain medium [74,75], offering excellent beam quality,
 24 reduced thermal issues, and outstanding scalability [76–78]. For instance, several demonstrations
 25 have reported, with one achieving a maximum power of 30 kW [79–81]. Theoretical studies
 26 suggest that DAPLs could scale to 100 kW while maintaining near diffraction-limited beam
 27 quality and excellent weight-to-power ratio, potentially outperforming DPSSLs and competing
 28 with fiber lasers for high-power CW applications [45,82]. Additionally, their emission
 29 wavelengths align with optimal absorption wavebands of main PV technologies, positioning
 30 DPALs as a promising option for laser power beaming [83].

31 As a summary, Table 2 presents the key characteristics for HPOT of the different types of lasers
 32 considered in this study.

33
 34 Table 2. Typical performance parameters for high-power semiconductor lasers (SCL), diode-
 35 pumped solid-state lasers (DPSSL), and diode-pumped alkali lasers (DPAL). Max P_{out} stands for
 36 maximum output power, λ for wavelength, M^2 for beam quality, and $\eta_{\text{E-O}}$ for electrical-to-optical
 37 conversion efficiency. (*) Northrop Grumman 105.5 kW -laser achieved a beam quality of $M^2 =$
 38 3 [84], while IPG Photonics reported a significantly higher $M^2 = 140$ for their 120 kW -laser [69].
 39 (**) Estimated values.

Type of laser	Max P_{out} (kW)	λ (nm)	M^2	Weight-to-power ratio (kg kW ⁻¹)	$\eta_{\text{E-O}}$ (%)
SCL	~ 10 [52]	400 - 3000 [49]	$\sim 10 - 100$ [52,85]	< 1 [85]	> 65 [86]
DPSSL	> 100 [69,84]	400 - 3000 [45]	$\sim 1 - 10$ * [69,84]	> 20 [69]	> 40 [69]
DPAL	30 [81]	700 - 900 [83]	< 3 [87]	7 [82]	$25 - 30$ ** [83]

40
 41 A special mention is given to *solar lasers*, as they represent a promising long-term alternative.
 42 Their operational principle relies on harnessing and concentrating sunlight to directly pump the

1 laser gain medium, usually a crystal or glass, although gaseous and liquid media are also used
2 [88]. As a result, a coherent, collimated and monochromatic beam is obtained without requiring
3 electrical or chemical power sources. This technology aligns with net-zero objectives, offering
4 fully renewable energy delivery solutions, particularly interesting for space-based HPOT
5 applications where powering the light source is challenging. However, significant improvements
6 are needed to address current limitations, such as reducing device size, enabling operation at
7 sunlight power density level, and increasing energy conversion efficiency, which remains below
8 10% [89]. Examples of lasers used in HPOT demonstrations are summarized in Table 3 (see
9 section 6.3).

10 Beyond lasers, alternative solar-pumped techniques include sustainable quasi-monochromatic
11 approaches such as luminescence solar concentrators [90] and holographic optical elements [91].
12 However, significant breakthroughs are required to make these technologies competitive with
13 lasers. Future development efforts are justified as they enable sustainable HPOT systems.

14 15 **4. Light propagation**

16 Light transmission at high-power levels is complex, as photons can be significantly influenced by
17 various phenomena upon emission, affecting both energy quality and quantity. These effects can
18 critically impact system viability, making it essential to understand how environmental properties
19 affect optical beams.

20 This section discusses key physical processes involved in high-power optical propagations,
21 including attenuation and divergence, along with insights on tracking and safety measures. Other
22 phenomena such as turbulence and thermal blooming are also briefly discussed. Given the early
23 stage of the technology, this article primary focuses on atmospheric transmissions, as it represents
24 the most convenient initial testing medium before advancing into more challenging scenarios,
25 such as underwater. Nonetheless, it is important to note that in space applications some of the
26 phenomena discussed in this work do not apply, since the propagation medium, i.e. vacuum, does
27 not contain particles that could physically interact with light. Since transmission through optical
28 fibers differs significantly from free space propagation, a dedicated section (section 4.4) is
29 included to further address it.

30 31 **4.1 Attenuation: absorption and scattering**

32 Light beam propagation through non-vacuum media is affected by atoms, molecules, and
33 aerosols, which absorb and scatter optical energy, reducing (attenuating) its power [92]. This
34 combined effect is described by the extinction coefficient, $\tau(\lambda) = \alpha(\lambda) + \beta(\lambda)$, where α and β are
35 the absorption and scattering contributions, respectively [93].

36 Attenuation characteristics vary significantly across media, as represented in Fig. 3. In water,
37 attenuation is minimal near 450 nm but increases sharply at shorter and longer wavelengths
38 [94,95]. In the case of the Earth's atmosphere, three different types of environments are
39 considered (see Fig. 3): standard, considered the reference in the PV field; wet, corresponding to
40 humid areas (water vapor = 4.11 cm); and hazy, related to extreme values of aerosols regions
41 (aerosol optical depth at 500 nm = 0.5) [96]. However, their attenuation patterns are very similar:
42 they slightly decrease with increasing wavelengths, although they exhibit some abrupt peaks due
43 to absorption by atmospheric constituents such as CO₂, O₂, H₂O, aerosols, etc, and due to Rayleigh
44 scattering at ultraviolet region. Additionally, it should be noted that weather conditions, such as
45 fog or rain, further intensify atmospheric losses [45]. [96] Lastly, optical fiber (assumed fused
46 silica) attenuation is dominated by Rayleigh scattering within the fiber below 1550 nm and by
47 infrared absorption at longer wavelengths, with a notable peak at 1380 nm caused by OH⁻ impurity
48 ion absorption from water dissolved in the glass [97].

49 Attenuation is strongly dependent on the photon wavelength. Therefore, it is crucial to select
50 sources that fit the attenuation profile of the medium. Referring to Fig. 3, suitable propagation
51 wavelengths for water fall within the 400 - 500 nm waveband, whereas for atmospheric

1 applications it would be advisable to avoid wavelengths in the vicinity of 950, 1150 and 1400 nm.
 2 Regarding optical fiber transmissions, three main transmission windows are usually considered,
 3 around 800, 1300 and 1550 nm [2].
 4

5
 6 Fig. 3. Attenuation as a function of wavelength for water, optical fiber (assumed pure fused silica),
 7 and three types of atmospheres (denoted as “Atm”): standard, wet, and hazy. Rayleigh scattering
 8 attenuation in optical fiber was added to serve as a reference for ultraviolet transmissions in fiber
 9 optics. Refer to Ref. [96,98] for more information about water and atmosphere, and to Ref. [97]
 10 in the case of optical fiber.

11
 12 Considering only attenuation losses, the optical input power (P_{in}) received by the OPCs can be
 13 estimated by means of the Beer-Lambert law [93,96,99]:
 14

$$15 \quad P_{in}(\lambda, d) = P_s \exp(-\tau(\lambda)d) \quad (1)$$

16
 17 where P_s is the power emitted by the source, and d is the distance travelled by the beam. Note
 18 that τ includes the attenuation produced by all constituents of the medium. This serves as a first
 19 estimate in system design, subject to further analysis of additional phenomena.
 20

21 4.2 Turbulence and thermal blooming

22 The OWPT system performance can be further compromised by other environmental phenomena,
 23 such as turbulence and thermal blooming. Turbulence arises from random refractive index (n)
 24 fluctuations in the propagation medium, primarily due to temperature gradients, and, in seawater,
 25 also due to salinity and dissipation rates [45,100]. It causes effects like scintillation, beam wander,
 26 and beam spread, which deteriorates the beam shape and the intensity, as shown in Fig. 4. In
 27 strong turbulence conditions (refractive-index structure parameter $C_n^2 > 10^{-13} \text{ m}^{-2/3}$), loss of
 28 coherence and beam breakup can occur. Mitigation strategies include aperture averaging and
 29 adaptive optics, and using longer wavelengths due to the inversely proportional relationship
 30 [93,101].
 31

Fig. 4. Intensity contours at the target plane for three levels of turbulence depending on constant refractive-index structure parameter (C_n^2): a) no turbulence ($C_n^2 = 0$), b) moderate ($C_n^2 = 10^{-14} \text{ m}^{-2/3}$), and c) strong ($C_n^2 = 10^{-13} \text{ m}^{-2/3}$). Image adapted from Ref. [102].

Thermal blooming, on the other hand, is a nonlinear optical effect caused by the absorption of a high-power laser energy by the medium, leading to localized heating and variations in n . This results in an expansion of the beam diameter, a reduction in I_p , and, in the presence of a transverse current, an off-target displacement, as illustrated in Fig. 5 [103–106]. This phenomenon can seriously compromise the performance of HPOT systems: in the atmosphere, thermal blooming becomes a concern for transmission distances of several kilometers and power levels in the range of hundreds of kilowatts [93], whereas in underwater environments, its impact is expected to be substantially more severe [104,107]. Mitigation strategies, such as medium vaporization, beam rotation, and closed-loop adaptive optics, can help reduce its effects [108,109].

Fig. 5. Thermal blooming effect: considering a Gaussian beam propagating in z direction (1), the absorption of energy by particles of the medium heats the surrounding environment (ΔT) (2), resulting in a negative refractive index gradient (Δn) (3). The fluctuations of n act as divergent lenses, causing the beam to defocus, leading to an intensity reduction and a transverse scattering of the contour of the beam (xy -plane) (4). In the presence of fluid (air or water) flowing in the x -axis direction (v_{\perp}), the beam would deviate towards the opposite direction ($-x$) (5). The change in the beam profile is illustrated in the lower graphs, adapted from Ref. [103]: a) the diffraction-limited case in the absence of thermal blooming, and b) the steady-state thermal blooming case with a transverse flow. The white circle represents the diffraction limit contour.

4.3 Beam divergence and peak intensity

Beam divergence is a critical parameter for long-distance HPOT, as it broadens the beam diameter as it propagates, potentially leading to spillage losses. Divergence must be minimized to obtain a beam spot compact enough for its integration in the desired target, especially for small ones such as drones or rovers, ensuring efficient energy transfer to the remote system, while also reducing weight, non-uniformity effects, and costs.

The received beam profile results from the combination of multiple factors, including wavelength, beam quality, and source aperture, as well as environmental and mechanical influences such as turbulence, thermal blooming, and mechanical jitter caused by system motion or vibrations from cooling mechanisms and wind loads, for example [46,47,110]. These phenomena can interact synergistically or counteract, complicating divergence estimation. For simplicity, divergence is modeled here for a basic atmospheric case, assuming a Gaussian beam profile. The total divergence or angular spread (θ_s) of a beam can be expressed as a combination of linear (θ_L) and non-linear effects, consisting solely of thermal blooming (θ_{TB}) in this particular case (for further insights, see Ref. [111,112]):

$$\theta_s^2 = \theta_L^2 + \theta_{TB}^2 \quad (2)$$

The linear term (θ_L) includes diffraction (θ_D), turbulence (θ_T), and jitter (θ_j). Simplifying for uniform beams, zero slew rate, and horizontal propagation with a constant C_n^2 , it can be expressed as:

$$\theta_L^2 = \theta_D^2 + \theta_T^2 + \theta_j^2 \quad (3)$$

For multi-mode lasers, the influence of beam quality (M^2) in its divergence is significant. For instance, it is considered to be more impactful than other linear effects, such as turbulence and diffraction [93]. Therefore, an additional term θ_Q should be added to equation (3) when using lasers of higher-order modes:

$$\theta_Q^2 = (M^2 - 1) \theta_D^2 \quad (4)$$

Finally, it is possible to estimate the peak intensity (I_p) received at a distance d as [111,112]:

$$I_p(\lambda, d) = (P_s \exp(-\tau(\lambda)d)) / (\pi d^2 \theta_s^2) \quad (5)$$

where the numerator corresponds to the attenuated power as defined in equation (1), and the denominator corresponds the area at the receiver for a far-field fundamental transverse electromagnetic mode Gaussian beam with divergence angle θ_s [113]. Prior to this formulation, Gebhardt [110] derived an empirical model accounting for both linear and non-linear detrimental effects. The analytical fit indicates that, although the peak irradiance increases with P_s , at some point, the heating produces a blooming of the beam area that overshadows the effect of the increased power, leading to a counterintuitive decline in light intensity as power rises. This curve is commonly called the power optimization curve. Other authors also state that strong turbulence can cause a similar effect [93].

4.4 Optical fiber

Optical fibers can only transmit up to a certain power level before experiencing physical damage or reduced functionality. If this limit is surpassed, some detrimental phenomena may arise. One of the most impactful effects is the so-called fiber fuse, which is characterized by the formation of a visible bright spot of white light, considered to be plasma due to the estimated high temperature (5000-10000 K) associated with the spectrum of the emitted light, that propagates by

1 thermal diffusion towards the origin of the light source at an approximate velocity of 1 m s^{-1} ,
2 leaving behind a bubble-shaped track of irreversible and catastrophic degradation on the optical
3 fiber core [114,115]. According to empirical observations [114,115], the power density threshold
4 for fiber fuse is in the order of MWcm^{-2} , and it is dependent on the fiber composition and laser
5 light wavelength.

6 However, solely exceeding the optical power threshold is insufficient to trigger the fiber fuse
7 effect. A localized high-temperature ignition point is also required. The origin of this localized
8 heating may come from different sources, such as from the energy leakage from the fiber core to
9 the cladding due to an excessive bending of the optical fiber cable (which can be a problem on its
10 own, as it can directly catch on fire), or from the absorption of the intense optical energy by
11 contaminated or degraded connectors within the fiber [116].

12 Besides fiber fuse, non-linear effects may also occur at high-power optical densities, such as
13 stimulated Brillouin and Raman scattering (SBS and SRS, respectively). These scattering
14 phenomena originate from the interaction of light with acoustic (SBS) and optical phonons (SRS),
15 and the intensity of the scattered light scales exponentially once the power threshold is exceeded
16 [117]. While light waves scattered under SBS propagates backwards, downshifting the frequency
17 several GHz, SRS can occur in both directions, changing the frequency of the scattered light in
18 the order of THz [118]. Additionally, other non-linear effects may also appear, such as self-phase
19 modulation (SPM) and cross-phase modulation (XPM). SPM is characterized by a phase shift of
20 the optical signal produced by a refractive index variation induced by the high-power optical
21 signal itself, whereas XPM occurs when multiple optical signals propagating through the same
22 fiber mutually alter their phases due to the fiber non-linear refractive index [119].

23 There are multiple fiber types suitable for PoF applications (Fig. 6) [120]. Single-mode fibers
24 offer low loss (0.2 dBkm^{-1} at 1550 nm) for long distances but face power density limitations due
25 to its small core. Conversely, multimode fibers can transmit higher powers due to its bigger core
26 (diameter ranges from 62.5 to $200 \mu\text{m}$), although simultaneous data transfer may be limited due
27 to modal dispersion and crosstalk. In cases where the target is the simultaneous information and
28 power transmission, specialized fibers like multicore fibers and double-clad fibers are the best
29 options, where the latter stands out for its enhanced high-power transfer capabilities. In this
30 context, hollow-core photonic crystal fibers and microstructured optical fibers are promising
31 solutions. Hollow-core photonic crystal fibers achieve ultra-low non-linearity and tolerance to
32 high powers in exchange of higher attenuation compared to silica fibers, whereas microstructured
33 optical fibers exhibit enhanced power thresholds in comparison to conventional fibers. In
34 conclusion, each architecture presents unique tradeoffs between power handling, data capacity,
35 and transmission efficiency.

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2 Fig. 6. Cross sections of various types of optical fibers. (a) Single-mode fiber, (b) multimode
3 fiber, (c) multicore fiber, (d) double-clad fiber, (e) hollow-core photonic crystal fiber, (f)
4 microstructured optical fiber. Image from Ref. [120].

5 6 **4.5 Tracking and safety**

7 The operation flexibility provided by OWPT is both a remarkable feature and a complex
8 challenge. This section briefly addresses tracking and safety considerations, which may initially
9 be overlooked.

10 Efforts to minimize propagation losses and optimize the PV components of the system are useless
11 if the beam is not accurately pointed at the target. A beam control system (illustrated in Fig. 7), is
12 recommended to ensure precise aiming and sustained alignment for tasks such as recharging
13 batteries or powering devices [49]. Typically, such systems consist of target-alerting and tracking
14 mechanisms, a system processor, a gimbal-control system for beam stability, an accurate pointing
15 mechanism, inertial sensors, a power supply, and an environmental protective cover. In dynamic
16 applications, aero-optical effects from fluid flow over the emitter induce turbulence and
17 refraction, reducing precision. Proper positioning of the beam director can mitigate these effects
18 [45].

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21 Fig. 7. Example of a high-power laser beam direction system for directed-energy applications
22 [121].

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24 In static configurations, beam alignment is relatively simple, but motion significantly complicates
25 the challenge. Solutions vary depending on pointing requirements. Autonomous beam trackers

1 have successfully powered moving targets [122–125], while simpler GPS-based and manual
 2 tracking systems have also been developed [20,126].
 3 Given the high source power densities involved, implementing safety measures is crucial,
 4 particularly in populated atmospheric environments where accidental exposure could cause severe
 5 injuries, including skin burns and retinal damage, or, in extremely rare cases, life-threatening
 6 hazards like skin cancer or electrocution risks (from power supply unit failures) [45,127].
 7 International safety standards to regulate laser hazards and protective measures have been set by
 8 the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC): “IEC 60825 Series” [128]. These norms are
 9 further implemented in national regulations; for example, the American National Standards
 10 Institute (ANSI) standard series ANSI Z136 [129].
 11 Three key safety parameters are considered: the Accessible Emission Limit (AEL), the Maximum
 12 Permissible Exposure (MPE), and the Nominal Ocular Hazard Distance (NOHD). Whereas the
 13 AEL defines the maximum accessible emission level and serves as the basis for laser
 14 classification, the NOHD represents the distance from the source at which radiation levels equal
 15 the MPE. Among the different safety parameters, the MPE is the most relevant in the context of
 16 this article, as it determines the maximum irradiance level the main organs at risk (eyes and skin)
 17 can be exposed to without suffering short or long-term damage, according to International
 18 Commission on Non-Ionizing Radiation Protection (ICNIRP) [130]. Visible and near-infrared
 19 wavelengths pose the greatest risk to vision, as retinal focusing amplifies power density roughly
 20 by a factor of 10^5 [131,132]. Fig. 8 shows the MPE variations with exposure time for various
 21 wavelengths per IEC 60825. Ultraviolet A (315 - 400 nm) and long-infrared wavebands are
 22 considered less harmful for exposure times of up to approximately 100 s. It is worth mentioning
 23 that the safety response time to shut off the beam is around 1 ms, allowing more powerful laser
 24 to be safely used within these wavebands [133]. Regarding skin hazards, the damage is more
 25 severe at shorter wavelengths, particularly injurious within the ultraviolet B range (280 – 315
 26 nm). Nonetheless, the hazards associated with skin exposure are of less importance than those for
 27 the eyes [127,134,135].
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 30 Fig. 8. Maximum permissible exposure (MPE) in Wcm^{-2} versus exposure time for various
 31 wavelengths based on IEC 60825 (Hankwang at English Wikipedia, via Wikimedia Commons
 32 [136]).
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34 Several strategies to address the safety concerns have been proposed. Wi-Charge and Tongji
 35 University researchers developed a resonant cavity-based system that maintains power within
 36 MPE limits [137–140]. PowerLight Technologies’ light curtain ensures that no obstacle is present
 37 along the beam propagation path by coaxially coupling a harmless beam with the primary laser

[9,141], similar to Washington University researchers' approach [16], and Aquila's three-tier lock system [142]. Other ideas based on advanced vision to detect objects entering a predefined safety zone and adjust P_S accordingly have also been developed [143].

5. Optical photovoltaic converters

Despite its origins dating back to 1977 [144], OPCs remain at critical bottleneck in advancing of HPOT technology [2,4]. This section outlines the fundamentals of OPCs, including their operating principles, primary loss mechanisms, and mitigation strategies, along with a comprehensive review of reported OPCs in the literature.

5.1 Ideal OPCs and intrinsic losses

OPCs are essentially PV cells optimized to efficiently convert monochromatic light into electricity. Ideally, illuminating a semiconductor with a wavelength matching its energy gap (E_g) would ensure complete photon collection without energy loss, as each photon provides precisely the energy needed to excite an electron into the conduction band. Unfortunately, this ideal scenario is unattainable in practice due to both intrinsic and extrinsic losses.

Intrinsic losses arise from unavoidable recombination processes during photovoltaic conversion. A thermodynamic analysis reveals that, under radiative recombination, the entropic losses from the absorption and emission of radiation are by far the dominant intrinsic loss mechanism [145]. However, these entropic losses can be significantly reduced by using wider bandgap semiconductors and increasing irradiance. These results are supported by similar studies in which the maximum theoretical efficiency for monochromatic illumination is calculated based on the radiative efficiency limit (also known as detailed balance limit or Shockley-Queisser limit [146]) [96,147]. As represented in Fig. 8 (left), for a constant input power density ($\rho_{in} = 100 \text{ Wcm}^{-2}$), the PV conversion efficiency (η_{PV}) improves with increasing E_g . This is primarily due to an enhancement in the fill factor (FF): higher E_g reduce intrinsic losses, and, as a consequence, the voltage at the maximum power point (V_{mpp}) shifts closer to the open-circuit voltage (V_{OC}), pushing the FF towards unity (Fig. 9, right). A similar effect occurs with increasing illumination, which is one of the key phenomena used in concentrator photovoltaics (CPV) to obtain superior efficiencies compared to standard non-concentrator PV technologies [148–150].

Fig. 9. Theoretical radiative photovoltaic efficiency (η_{PV}) limit (left), and fill factor (FF) and the ratio of the voltage at the maximum power point (V_{mpp}) and open-circuit voltage (V_{OC}) (right) as a function of energy gap. Assumptions: ideal photon absorption, external quantum efficiency (EQE) of 100%, temperature of 298 K, and energy gap equal to hc/λ , being h the Planck constant and c the speed of light. Note: since this section exclusively considers intrinsic losses, resistive losses are neglected for now, but they will be addressed in the next section.

Intrinsic losses also include other recombination mechanisms of non-radiative nature, such as Auger, defect-assisted, and surface recombination. While Auger recombination has minimal

1 impact on direct-band semiconductors unless carrier concentrations are extremely high [145,151–
 2 153], it represents a concern for indirect-band semiconductors, such as silicon [153,154]. These
 3 losses can be reduced by implementing textured surfaces, and spectral and angular filters which
 4 enhance light absorption, effectively equivalent to increasing incident irradiance, thereby
 5 improving efficiency [145]. On the other hand, recombination through defect traps or impurities
 6 can degrade device performance [155–157]. Growth complexities in some materials introduce
 7 structural defects that act as recombination centers. The associated losses can be reduced by
 8 improving the semiconductor quality through advanced growth techniques [158–160].

10 5.2 Extrinsic losses and mitigation strategies

11 In practical scenarios, extrinsic losses are inevitable. This section provides an overview of the
 12 primary sources of extrinsic losses, emphasizing the key challenges OPCs must overcome to
 13 achieve high efficiencies.

14 - *Series resistance.* PV cells exhibit parasitic series resistance (R_S) due to the inherent
 15 opposition of materials to charge carrier flow. This resistance arises from several physical
 16 mechanisms, with the primary contributors being the bulk resistance of the semiconductor
 17 material, the resistance of metallic contacts, and the resistance of the metal-semiconductor
 18 interface [151]. Its negative impact on device performance becomes a major concern at high ρ_{in} ,
 19 as the associated power losses scale quadratically with current as $I^2 R_S$. As a result, efficiency tends
 20 to increase logarithmically with irradiance until the effect of R_S takes over, drastically worsening
 21 device performance thereafter [2,96,98].

22 The impact of R_S in the performance of the OPCs is illustrated in Fig. 10, where the theoretical
 23 radiative efficiency limit is calculated for materials with low (1.0 eV) and high (3.0 eV) E_g . Two
 24 scenarios are considered: an ideal case ($R_S = 0 \Omega\text{cm}^{-2}$) and realistic case ($R_S = 10^{-3} \Omega\text{cm}^{-2}$). The
 25 results show that as ρ_{in} exceeds the 100 Wcm^{-2} threshold, R_S losses become increasingly
 26 significant, particularly for the lower bandgap material, where the η_{PV} deviates substantially from
 27 the ideal projection (dashed line). The reason behind it is that, for a fixed ρ_{in} and assuming high
 28 energy gap materials are illuminated with shorter wavelength light beams, wider bandgap
 29 semiconductors receive fewer (but more energetic) photons than narrower bandgap materials,
 30 according to Einstein’s photoelectric law. Consequently, the photogenerated current is inherently
 31 lower in wider bandgap OPCs, ultimately reducing their R_S losses [96].

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 34 Fig. 10. Photovoltaic efficiency (η_{PV}) of low- (1.0 eV, blue) and high- (3.0 eV, green) energy gap
 35 materials, considering an ideal ($R_S = 0 \Omega\text{cm}^{-2}$, dashed lines) and a realistic ($R_S = 10^{-3} \Omega\text{cm}^{-2}$, solid
 36 lines with markers) scenario of series resistance values (assumptions described in Fig. 9).

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R_s is considered the main limiting factor of η_{PV} at high irradiances. Taking this into account, there are several approaches to mitigate its severe detrimental impact. One option focuses on cell architecture, where two types of structures can be signaled (see Fig. 11): horizontal, light falls on the top surface of the cell normal to the n-p junction plane; and vertical (also known as edge-illuminated), the device is illuminated parallelly to the n-p junction plane. In both configurations, it is possible to manufacture multi-junction (MJ) structures where each subcell can be interconnected in series either vertically or horizontally.

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Fig. 11. a) and b) schematically illustrate horizontal and vertical n-p homojunction OPCs, respectively. Yellow arrows indicate the direction of incident illumination and metal contacts are represented in grey color. n and p represent the doping type of the layers, with the + sign denoting high doping concentration. Pictures c) and d) show different shapes and grid configuration examples of front surfaces of vertical architectures.

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Considering horizontal structures, the front contact grid should be optimized according to the expected ρ_{in} and semiconductor bandgap, adjusting the pattern, width and spacing of the metallic fingers [161,162]. This architecture particularly benefits from a MJ approach, since it reduces R_s losses by splitting the total current across its multiple subcells. [161,162] Moreover, including a transparent heavily-doped lateral conduction layer on top of the window layer mitigates R_s impact, since it ultimately increases the lateral conductivity and collection of majority carriers [163].

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Vertical architectures, on the other hand, offer advantages such as the mitigation of R_s losses due to the large cross-sectional contact area available for current flow, as the metal electrodes are located laterally. Also, this configuration allows for a drastic reduction of the current density due to the orthogonal incidence of the light on the p-n junctions and the current flow [164,165]. In this sense, vertical structures reduce device internal resistance and eliminates the trade-off between R_s and front contact shadowing [166,167]. The main issue lies in achieving sufficiently large areas for optical energy harvesting. Currently, the most promising solution involves the use of MJ structures connected via tunnel junctions [164,165]. The manufacture of this structure, however, is still challenging due to technical limitations, although there are some examples in the literature regarding its feasibility [168,169].

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Material selection also plays an important role. Wider bandgap semiconductors require fewer but more energetic photons to collect the same energy as narrower bandgap semiconductors, resulting in less photogenerated current, thereby reducing R_s losses [96,98,163]. Additionally, thermal annealing techniques mitigates R_s losses by enhancing electrodes ohmic contact [170]. Nevertheless, this process must be carefully optimized to prevent degrade contact quality or accelerate device degradation. Precise control of temperature, duration, and ambient conditions is essential to achieve optimal ohmic contacts while minimizing adverse effects [171].

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- *Beam non-uniformity.* Non-uniform illumination frequently occurs in HPOT, as non-flat-top Gaussian profiles are the most typical laser beam profiles. These non-uniform irradiance

1 distributions deteriorate OPC performance, particularly reducing the FF and V_{OC} [172,173].
2 Moreover, localized peak irradiances lead to lateral current spreading and current overdriving in
3 certain areas of the front surface, increasing resistive losses [174–176]. The impact is considerably
4 more severe in horizontally connected horizontal structures, also called multi-segment, where the
5 photocurrent is limited by the subcell producing the lowest current, resulting in significant
6 mismatch losses [177]. In contrast, vertically stacked monolithic MJ OPCs are less affected by
7 non-uniformities, as the lower current flowing through each subcell mitigates the associated R_S
8 losses. A potential drawback worth to mention of these structures is that their performance can be
9 degraded if the peak current density of the tunnel junctions is exceeded, which could happen in
10 rare cases of intense non-uniform irradiance [172,178]. In practice, nowadays, the peak current
11 density of well-engineered state-of-the-art tunnel junctions (several thousands of Acm^{-2} [178–
12 181]) has proven to not represent a limiting factor for most mature materials[182], since the R_S
13 losses would impact the OPC's performance before reaching those intense power densities [183].

14 Non-uniformity losses can be minimized by optimizing the grid design to balances the trade-off
15 between power losses from metal contact shadowing and from non-uniform illumination [172].
16 An alternative approach to achieve uniform illumination is the use of spherical enclosed receivers
17 called powerspheres [184,185]. Additionally, drawing on the experience of the scientific
18 community in the field of CPV, another potential strategy could involve homogenizers, such as
19 dielectric-cross compound-parabolic-concentrator (DCCPC), single-lens-optical element (SILO-
20 Pyramid) or refractive truncated pyramid (RTP) [186]. To the best of the authors' knowledge,
21 these approaches have not yet been applied in HPOT. Based on the author's CPV experience,
22 implementing these elements is expected to enhance the performance and the dimensions of
23 HPOT large receivers made up of several OPCs while minimizing semiconductor material usage
24 [187–189].

25 *Temperature.* OPCs often operate outside their optimal temperature range, from cryogenic
26 conditions (~ 200 °C) [190] to extreme heat scenarios (~ 180 °C) [170], significantly impacting
27 efficiency. Fundamentally, higher temperatures reduce the semiconductor E_g , limiting V_{OC} , and,
28 ultimately, the η_{PV} . Furthermore, this issue particularly affects MJ horizontal architectures, where
29 the bandgap and absorption coefficient variations can induce current mismatches among the
30 subcells. To minimize this effect, and almost eliminate it, both the OPC structure and the laser
31 wavelength must be optimized for the intended temperature operating conditions [191]. In this
32 sense, it has been shown that performance degradation can be limited to a maximum of
33 approximately 15% even under an extreme temperature variation range (~ 100 °C) [192,193].
34 Additionally, mechanisms such as luminescent coupling, where photons emitted from radiative
35 recombination in current-overproducing subcells are re-absorbed by current-limiting subcells,
36 help mitigate current mismatches [194,195]. Nevertheless, the reduction in V_{OC} is considered the
37 largest contributor to the performance degradation, as in standard solar cells [193,196].
38 [192]Extreme thermal stress can also end up damaging the cell or its components [197].

39 Additional strategies to mitigate temperature effects include the use of thermal packaging or
40 cooling mechanisms [198]. Another promising approach involves integrating thermoelectric
41 generators to maintain the OPC operating at its optimal point while simultaneously increasing η_E
42 by harnessing the excess heat [199]. Thermal losses can be further reduced by using wider
43 bandgap semiconductors and increasing irradiance [200,201]. This approach reduces the absolute
44 value of the temperature coefficient (T_C), a common parameter in PV for assessing the influence
45 of temperature on device performance. These phenomena have been extensively studied and
46 experimentally validated in MJ concentrator solar cells under ultra-high light intensities
47 [202,203]. Fig. 12 shows the T_C of V_{OC} , the parameter that mainly explain the temperature
48 dependence of PV devices, as a function of E_g for various illumination intensities in order to
49 illustrate both effects previously mentioned [204].

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3 Fig. 12. Relative temperature coefficient (T_C) of open-circuit voltage (V_{OC}) at 298 K as a function
 4 of energy gap for various input light intensities. As a first approximation, it is considered that the
 5 temperature dependence of OPCs is primarily driven by variations in V_{OC} . The calculations are
 6 based on the radiative efficiency limit approach and using the expressions from Ref. [205],
 7 assuming negligible temperature-induced variations in the photo-generated current, fill factor and
 8 energy gap.

9 Nonetheless, OPCs often exhibit notable resilience to high-temperature conditions, maintaining a
 10 reduced but reliable level of functionality [170]

11 - *Other losses:* beyond the aforementioned sources, additional losses can further
 12 compromise OPC performance. These include optical losses, such as spillage losses, which occur
 13 when light falls outside the active area of the device [2,177], as well as misalignment losses,
 14 arising when light falls outside the acceptance angle of the cell [206]. Other common losses in
 15 conventional PV also apply, including thermal stress from sudden temperature variations
 16 (particularly under intermittent intense irradiance), mechanical strain, suboptimal system
 17 connections, humidity, soiling, and degradation due to radiation, to name a few [207,208].

18

19 Extrinsic losses have a critical negative impact on η_{PV} . Therefore, a thorough analysis and
 20 understanding of these losses are essential for advancing this technology.

21

22 5.3 OPCs performance overview

23 To illustrate the current capabilities of OPCs, Fig. 13 presents a comprehensive compilation of
 24 data reported in the literature that was accessible to the authors. The chart shows the maximum
 25 η_{PV} achieved by OPCs based on their semiconductor material as a function of the light source
 26 wavelength and ρ_{in} , represented using a red-tone scale. It should be noted that information
 27 regarding ρ_{in} is not always explicitly provided; in such cases, it was calculated from available
 28 data, assuming that the illuminated spot corresponded to the device active area unless specified
 29 otherwise. If the reference does not provide enough data to perform that estimation, the marker
 30 was left blank. Additionally, some results were obtained under broadband flash-lamp
 31 illuminations and converted to the desired wavelength using spectral response measurements,
 32 rather than directly using monochromatic sources. In light of the diversity of measurement
 33 approaches, standardization, although challenging [209–211], is urgently needed, not only to
 34 ensure reliability and quality of the results, but also to guarantee that measurements are
 35 reproducible and comparable across studies, as already emphasized by some researchers [183].

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2 Fig. 13. Maximum photovoltaic efficiencies (η_{PV}) reported in literature as a function of light
3 source wavelength [126,144,147,163,170,173,183,190,191,196,212–293]. Input power density
4 (ρ_{in}) is represented with a logarithmic red-scale side-bar from 10^{-3} to 10^4 Wcm^{-2} (marker left blank
5 if required data is not provided). Relevant energy gaps for some of the most popular materials are
6 represented as vertical dashed lines to easily visualized how close the laser wavelength is to this
7 limit: InGaN (3.03 eV [294]), GaInP (1.85 eV [217]), GaAs (1.42 eV [283]), Si (1.12 eV [48]),
8 GaInAs (1.15 eV [253], 1.07 eV [275], 0.86 eV [263], 0.74 eV [190,195]), InGaAsP (1.08 eV
9 [291], 0.89 eV [263]). Grey curves represent the theoretical radiative efficiency limits (RL) at 10
10 and 100 Wcm^{-2} (assumptions described in Fig. 9, with $R_s = 0$). (1) Including AlGaAs and
11 GaAs/AlGaAs heterostructures-based OPCs; (2) Including AlGaInAs-based OPCs; (3) Group
12 consisting of CIS, CIGS, Ge, perovskites and organic OPCs.

13
14 As shown in Fig. 13, GaAs-based devices are by far the most abundant OPCs, accounting for
15 roughly half of the total, and the most extensively studied, with early examples dating back to
16 1978 [42,295]. These devices achieve the highest η_{PV} , 34 of the top 35 efficiencies, including the
17 room temperature (298 K) record of 68.9% at 858 nm [283], as well as the low temperature (150
18 K) record of 74.7% at 808 nm [196]. The success of GaAs can be attributed to its maturity,
19 reliability, high efficiency, established presence across various PV fields, and the availability of
20 lasers with suitable wavelengths [2,22,193]. Remarkably, the mean η_{PV} of over 50 GaAs-based
21 OPCs gathered in this analysis is 56%.

22 In contrast, the efficiencies of other materials are significantly lower, generally under 55%, with
23 the exception of a GaInAs-based OPC achieving a notable η_{PV} of 67.5% at 77 K, the third highest
24 value [190]. For wavelengths greater than 900 nm, GaInAs and InGaAsP dominate, with η_{PV} up
25 to 54.7% [253] and 52.8% [263], respectively, while GaSb is used for the longest wavelengths,
26 exhibiting a 49.0% η_{PV} at 1680 nm [266]. For short wavelengths (<700 nm), GaInP leads with η_{PV}
27 records of 59.7% at 638 nm [193], and 59.1% at 590 nm [289]. Recently, wide-bandgap OPCs
28 based on InGaN demonstrated η_{PV} as high as 43.7% in the ultraviolet region (<400 nm), but at
29 very low ρ_{in} , 5 $mWcm^{-2}$ [214]. It is noteworthy that emerging PV technologies, such as thin-film
30 CIS, CIGS, perovskites, and organic PV cells, are also gradually entering this field [222–226].

31 Most of the reported peak efficiencies are obtained within the 1 - 100 Wcm^{-2} range, except for
32 extreme cases with tiny laser spots, of the order of hundredths of mm^2 , notably elevating the
33 power density to values well above 1000 W/cm^2 [235,259,270], or, conversely, other examples
34 using very low-power lasers, operating at $\rho_{in} \sim 10^{-3}$ Wcm^{-2} [214,215].

35 For comparison with the ideal upper limit, the theoretical radiative efficiency limit for 10 and 100
36 Wcm^{-2} are also plotted in Fig. 13. The results indicate that OPCs based on the most developed

1 materials, such as GaAs and GaInAs, are impressively close to this limit, while materials with
 2 higher E_g , such as InGaN and GaInP, whose theoretical η_{PV} projections are even higher, still have
 3 significant room for improvement.

4 It is also important to mention that, while ρ_{in} serves as a useful metric for comparing device
 5 performance across studies, practical applications ultimately depend on their output power (P_{out}).
 6 To further contextualize the results, Fig. 14 presents data for the same OPCs shown in Fig. 13 in
 7 terms of their input and output power (P_{out}).
 8

9
 10 Fig. 14. Photovoltaic efficiency (η_{PV}) and output power (P_{out}) of the existing OPCs in literature
 11 versus their respective input power (P_{in}) [126,147,163,170,173,183,190,191,196,212–293]. In
 12 cases where data is not explicitly given, values are calculated from available information. (1)
 13 Including AlGaAs and GaAs/AlGaAs heterostructures-based OPCs; (2) Including AlGaInAs-
 14 based OPCs; (3) Group consisting of CIS, CIGS, Ge, perovskites and organic OPCs.

15
 16 As expected, the most developed materials, GaAs and GaInAs, efficiently withstand P_{in} above 10
 17 W, alongside a Si-based OPC achieving a remarkable 35.0% η_{PV} at $P_{in}=25$ W [126]. While fewer
 18 than 20% of the collected references report P_{out} exceeding 1 W, some OPCs are already capable
 19 of delivering over 20 W, with a maximum of 29.5 W at its peak η_{PV} , 61% [282], followed by 22
 20 W at a η_{PV} of 49% [271]. Higher P_{out} values are certainly achievable, although this comes at the
 21 cost of a decrease in η_{PV} . This is strongly correlated with the size of the devices, as most OPCs
 22 are in the mm^2 range, where R_S and temperature losses begin to degrade performance at relatively
 23 low P_{in} . In practical terms, the implementation of OPCs would require further development of
 24 larger area devices while maintaining comparable performance levels, which may not be a trivial
 25 challenge.

26 Finally, it is worth mentioning that some OPCs are now commercially available from leading
 27 international suppliers such as Broadcom, Azur Space, or Spectrolab. This market availability
 28 represents a significant milestone in the maturation and commercialization of OPC technology,
 29 facilitating broader adoption and further development of these optoelectronic devices.

31 6. Applications and state-of-the-art HPOT systems

32 HPOT has recently gained widespread attention, entering an effervescent phase of practical
 33 development driven by its diverse applications and its potential to revolutionize the energy
 34 delivery paradigm. Highly versatile, this technology is adaptable to nearly any scenario. Unlike
 35 other WPT technologies based on capacitive, inductive, or magnetic resonance coupling, which
 36 are limited to near-field scenarios, HPOT stands out for its effective operation capability in far-

1 field applications, directly competing with microwave technology [28]. Nonetheless, it is
2 important to emphasize that HPOT is certainly not adequate for every context; its suitability will
3 depend on technical, economic, legal, and even social factors such as public acceptance. With this
4 in mind, HPOT applications can be broadly divided into two main groups: space and terrestrial
5 applications [1].

6 7 **6.1 Space applications**

8 Historically, power beaming has been closely tied to the space sector (see section 2 for more
9 details). The absence of an atmosphere in space eliminates potential losses caused by suspended
10 particles (mainly absorption, scattering, and thermal blooming), making HPOT ideal for in-space
11 power transmission between satellites and spacecraft. This is particularly useful in scenarios with
12 insufficient sunlight, such as eclipses, distant locations from the Sun, or powering small space
13 vehicles with limited energy storage, or without light, such as the dark side of the Moon.
14 Numerous studies have explored the fundamental challenges of satellite capabilities, focusing on
15 crucial factors for the success of long-duration space missions, such as design, lifespan, and travel
16 range [296–303].

17 The rapid progress in lunar exploration and industrialization is driving significant energy
18 demands. Transmitting power to challenging regions, such as craters and permanently shadowed
19 areas, remains a critical issue [1,304–306]. Given the faint atmosphere of the Moon (for most
20 practical purposes it can be assumed vacuum [307]), optical energy transmission is expected to
21 be efficient due to high η_T . As a result, various promising energy distribution strategies based on
22 HPOT have been explored, including orbiting satellites and lunar power bases
23 [22,24,38,40,41,308–314]. Similarly, HPOT systems have been proposed for other planets, such
24 as Mars, whose rather thin atmosphere allows efficient optical energy propagation (with some
25 absorption wavebands similar to Earth’s [315]), and Venus, whose dense gaseous atmosphere
26 limits transmission to a few viable windows [310,316].

27 Space application ambition does not stop there. Indeed, designs for space-based solar power
28 (SBSP) stations and rocket propulsion supplying the energy from Earth to space utilizing large-
29 scale HPOT systems have been studied [3,26,31,317–320]. Another remarkable benefit of HPOT
30 technology is its potential ability to transfer uninterrupted, 24/7, clean solar energy harvested by
31 future SBSP stations to Earth, thus mitigating the energy storage issues of terrestrial PV
32 technology. This is, for instance, aligned with the ESA under the “SOLARIS - towards a clean
33 and secure energy future for European citizens” initiative, which aims to cover 1/3 of the EU
34 energy demand within the next decade [321]. This opens up novel frontiers to find unexplored
35 resources to mitigate the energy and economic challenges of our era to contribute to the economic
36 growth, improving the living conditions of humanity over the next decades [12].

37 38 **6.2 Terrestrial applications**

39 The variety of applications on Earth does not fall short of space applications. Demonstrating high
40 precision tracking and robust safety features, HPOT technology is well-suited for both domestic
41 and industrial environments [10]. It has been demonstrated that it is possible to wirelessly
42 recharge via lasers small consumer electronic devices used in residential and workplace settings,
43 such as smartphones, tablets, or cameras, enhancing user convenience [16]. HPOT also supports
44 energy-demanding and mobile equipment commonly found in factory supply chains, like
45 warehouse robots, boosting efficiency in high-volume manufacturing by enabling continuous
46 operation [19,126].

47 In many cases, direct electrical power for electronic equipment is impractical or unsafe [2]. These
48 restricted areas, generally called exclusion regions, include toxic environments and scenarios with
49 high fire or explosion risks (e.g. refineries, mines, fuel tanks and aircrafts) [322,323], regions with
50 intense electromagnetic interference (e.g. nuclear plants, high energy physics experiments)
51 [324,325], and applications requiring galvanic insulation (e.g. high-voltage lines, lightning-

protected monitoring) [326–328]. Optical power transmission, either through air or fiber, minimizes these hazards. Moreover, HPOT enables simultaneous communication and power transmission [6,329,330], a key feature for sensors placed in harsh environments used in military missions [1,15] and for rechargeable batteries of medical devices, such as pacemakers and other body implants [17,18,331–333].

Other attractive terrestrial applications include not only remote powering of ground and aerial vehicles, such as rovers, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), and small aircrafts [20–23,32,47,334], but also subaquatic equipment, like autonomous underwater vehicles (AUVs) [11,335–339]. By enabling energy replenishment at a distance, HPOT extends device mobility indefinitely, eliminating the need for interruptions to return to recharging stations. This allows for more efficient design, as less storage capacity is required, reducing weight. Such capabilities have a tremendous potential impact in numerous sectors, such as agriculture, security (e.g. rescue missions, disaster response), surveillance (e.g. wildlife, environmental infrastructure, law enforcement, military), exploration missions (e.g. deep ocean, extremely hot environments), communication (e.g. support to radio access networks), transportation, and entertainment [1,13]. In some of those fields, uninterrupted availability is imperative, and HPOT can meet these needs. Lastly, HPOT could enhance traditional power grids, offering a lightweight alternative to copper wires (fiber optic cables weigh 3.6 times less [32]).

6.3 Overview of HPOT experimental demonstrations

Optical power transmission is not a new concept, with experiments dating back to the late 20th century [226]. Since then, numerous proof-of-concept studies have been conducted, significantly increasing activity over the last decade. These experiments have targeted a wide range of applications, ranging from small aerial and underwater vehicles [20–23,296,309,334,336] to sensors and other electronic devices [32,228,340,341]. Recently, the first in-space HPOT was successfully demonstrated, proving the technology’s capability to power real-world devices in various environments [298]. Fig. 15 presents an overview of reported HPOT experiments, showing their η_{E-E} , laser wavelengths employed, and transmission distances across different media: the atmosphere, water, fiber, and outer space.

Fig. 15. Survey of the HPOT systems reported in the literature [6,12,20–23,32,33,126,207,227,228,239,277–280,296,298,299,309,330,334–338,340–361]. The figure shows the end-to-end efficiencies (η_{E-E}) and distances achieved by the gathered demonstrations. Data points are color-coded to indicate the light source wavelength and categorized by marker shape to represent the transmission medium: atmosphere, optical fiber, water, or outer space. White-colored markers indicate that the laser wavelength is not disclosed in the reference. Note: if η_{E-E} is not explicitly provided, it is calculated as $\eta_{E-O} \times \eta_T \times \eta_{O-E}$. In cases where η_{E-O} and/or η_{O-E}

η_E are not detailed or cannot be estimated from available data, they are approximated as $\eta_{E-O}=\eta_S$ and $\eta_{O-E}=\eta_{PV}$. For more details on η_{E-O} , refer to the caption of Table 3.

The atmosphere is the most frequent medium for OWPT demonstrations, accounting for more than half of the documented experiments. These systems exhibit moderate η_{E-E} , generally below 10%, with transmission distances ranging from a few meters up to 1200 m, the longest reported distance for OWPT [309]. The highest η_{E-E} achieved in atmospheric OWPT is 18.1% at a distance of 10 m [227]. GaAs-based OPCs are the most widely used, with lasers usually operating in the 800 - 900 nm waveband.

For underwater OWPT, the available examples are scarce. Due to the severe attenuation of water, transmission distances are limited to 1 meter or less, with η_{E-E} usually lower than those of atmospheric OWPT, although a notable η_{E-E} of 9.2% has been obtained (assuming a η_{E-O} of 30%) [337]. The most efficient underwater systems rely on GaInP OPCs and employ 532 nm-wavelength lasers.

Regarding in-space OWPT, only one case has been reported to date, to the best of authors' knowledge. In 2023, approximately 1.5 W of almost uninterrupted power was transmitted for over 100 days to an OPC at a distance of 1.45 m, achieving a remarkable η_{E-E} of around 11% [298]. Unfortunately, the material of the OPC and the light source wavelength were not disclosed.

Beyond OWPT systems, PoF systems have also been widely studied, with numerous reported experiments. Optical fibers enable transmissions over significantly longer distances than OWPT, reaching tens of kilometers [341,344,349,350]. Their efficiencies are similar to that of atmospheric OWPT systems, except for the record η_{E-E} of 25.1%, achieved at a distance of 50 m [32]. 55% of the OPCs used in these systems are based on GaAs and GaInAs, with laser wavelengths around 800 - 900 nm and 1500 nm.

As for the emitter systems employed, Table 3 summarizes the available information about the light sources utilized in the experiments, all based in lasers. SCLs, particularly LDs, are the most widely used light source in the field due to their efficiency, versatility, and availability. Their broad spectral coverage across nearly the entire solar spectrum enables precise wavelength selection to optimize OPC performance, and they are capable of delivering relatively high P_S , enough for the targeted applications. For wavelengths longer than 1000 nm, fiber and SSLs are often used employed.

Table 3. Emitter systems used in HPOT experiments. The table provides information on the transmission medium, laser type, number of lasers employed, nominal power, wavelength, and electrical-to-optical efficiency (η_{E-O}). (*) indicates that η_{E-O} is calculated from data included in the reference; if only η_S is provided, then $\eta_{E-O}=\eta_S$ is assumed. (**) When estimations defined in (*) cannot be performed due to insufficient information, $\eta_{E-O} = 30\%$ is assumed. Note: Ref. [360] cautioned a η_S of few percent, thus a $\eta_{E-O} = 10\%$ was assumed.

Medium	Type of laser	P_S (W)	λ (nm)	η_{E-O} (%)	Reference
Atmosphere	LD	1500	940	50	[20]
	LD	1162	808	49	[278]
	LD	24	793	30	[239]
	LD	2500	810	**	[334]
	LD	500	808	47*	[22]
	LD	1.04	810	29*	[355]
	2x LD	-	660	27	[356]
	2x LD	200	808	30	[23]
	2x LD	2046	810	**	[361]
	3x LD	1.04	810	29*	[352]
4x LD	1.53	850	30	[354]	

	9x LD	1.53	850	**	[353]
	VCSEL	-	850	26*	[330]
	VCSEL	-	975	17	[351]
	5x VCSEL	2	850	42	[279]
	SCL	-	808	**	[207]
	SCL	-	808	**	[296]
	SCL	32	812	29*	[342]
	SCL	60	812	29*	[309]
	Disk	8000	1030	34	[126]
	Fiber	800	1070	30	[359]
	Fiber	50	1550	13	[280]
	Fiber	1.2	635	**	[277]
	SSL	8	532	**	[21]
	SSL	200	1064	**	[360]
	SSL	-	609	**	[357]
Fiber	LD	-	1550	15	[350]
	LD	1	810	**	[228]
	LD	0.25	1550	12*	[350]
	LD	15	1470	15	[350]
	LD	15	809	31*	[6]
	LD	12	808	37*	[299]
	LD	10	976	36*	[33]
	LD	2	1470	14*	[344]
	LD	15	808	45	[32]
	LD	0.5	1510	11*	[349]
	LD	30	915	30	[343]
	LD	30	940	30	[343]
	3x LD	1	976	**	[340]
	4x LD	35	808	45	[348]
	5x LD	3	808	15	[345]
	4x SCL	1.5	808	16	[346]
	Fiber	10	1480	8	[341]
	Fiber	3	1480	**	[347]
Water	LD	500	450	50	[336]
	LD	0.1	661	46	[335]
	Fiber	-	532	**	[337]

1

2 Finally, the adoption of international standards for reporting experimental results of HPOT is
3 strongly encouraged, as many reviewed references lack meaningful information.

4

5 7. Conclusions

6 The emergence of high-power optical transmission (HPOT) technology entails a potential shift of
7 the energy delivery paradigm as it is understood today. This transformative technology offers the
8 prospect of reaching previously inaccessible locations, from the deep sea to outer space, enabling
9 sustainable remote power transmission of kilowatts over distances of hundreds of kilometers.
10 Optical power is immune to electromagnetic noise, provides galvanic insulation, and allows the
11 simultaneous transfer of power and data. Consequently, HPOT presents a smart alternative to
12 traditional wiring in scenarios where the latter is risky, or simply neither feasible nor

1 recommended. Although the concept originated decades ago, it is only now, driven by the need
2 to meet emerging application demands where traditional technology is unfeasible, that HPOT is
3 flourishing.

4 This work aims to provide a comprehensive review of HPOT systems, both optical wireless
5 power transmission (OWPT) and power-over-fiber (PoF), examining their components,
6 applications, and recent technological advancements. Following a brief historical overview of the
7 origins and the evolution of HPOT, the emitter system is discussed, where different types of
8 potential light sources are identified. Based on the requirements of HPOT, lasers emerge as a clear
9 choice, although other prospective alternatives may play a role in the future. Among lasers,
10 semiconductor ones, particularly laser diodes, stand out for their high efficiency, availability, and
11 relatively low-cost. For long-distance, power-demanding applications, however, diode-pumped
12 solid-state lasers may be a more appropriate choice mainly due to their high output powers.

13 The selection of the light source is heavily influenced by the medium through which transmission
14 occurs. Attenuation of optical energy is a key concern, as a substantial fraction of the emitted
15 power could be lost on their way to the target. Therefore, it is crucial to analyze the specific
16 attenuation pattern of the medium to select optimal wavebands for transmission. In atmospheric
17 and underwater applications, other phenomena, such as divergence, turbulence, and thermal
18 blooming, also significantly affect light propagation and must be carefully considered and
19 mitigated where possible. In turbulent media or using extreme high-power beams, system
20 performance may be severely compromised. Additionally, beam divergence must be controlled
21 to ensure practical implementation.

22 A thorough analysis of optical photovoltaic converters (OPCs) is also carried out, with special
23 emphasis on their intrinsic and extrinsic loss mechanisms and corresponding mitigation strategies.
24 Performance degradation due to series resistance, temperature, and beam non-uniformity are
25 identified as major challenges that these devices must overcome to reach higher efficiency levels.
26 Furthermore, a comprehensive compilation of OPCs results from the literature is presented,
27 illustrating the clear dominance of GaAs and related semiconductors. Noteworthy efficiencies of
28 68.9% (298 K) and 74.7% (150 K) have been achieved at wavelengths of 858 and 808 nm,
29 respectively. However, both shorter (<700 nm) and longer (>900 nm) wavelengths remain areas
30 where, theoretically, OPCs have still room to improve, with ongoing research indicating progress
31 in this regard.

32 Finally, the potential applications of HPOT systems for both terrestrial and space environments
33 are explored. The range of possibilities is vast, including the powering of rovers, aerial and
34 subaquatic vehicles, sensors, pacemakers, and satellites, to name a few cases. HPOT is set to make
35 an immediate impact in sectors such as energy, defense, and healthcare, among others,
36 significantly enhancing their capabilities. Moreover, the HPOT demonstrations conducted to date,
37 to the best of the authors' knowledge, are presented, covering all types of transmission media:
38 atmosphere, water, space, and fiber optics. Remarkable transmission distances exceeding 10 km
39 and end-to-end efficiencies of 25.1% have already been achieved, reflecting persistent efforts to
40 drive technological progress and boost overall performance.

41 This work provides an overview of HPOT technology, highlighting key milestones and offering
42 perspective on the results reported in the literature. It presents the current state of the art, identifies
43 both strengths and weaknesses, and suggests potential development pathways for improving
44 system performance. While significant progress has been made, further work is necessary to
45 enhance the efficiency of both emitter and receiver systems, as well as to mitigate light
46 propagation losses, given the current limitations in overall performance. Nonetheless, considering
47 the broad range of potential applications and recent technological advancements, HPOT holds the
48 promise to revolutionize the energy sector, opening new horizons previously thought
49 unattainable. Among this, it opens the possibility to transfer uninterrupted, 24/7, clean solar
50 energy harvested by future space-based solar power stations to earth, thus mitigating the energy
51 storage issues of terrestrial PV technology. This paves the way for discovering untapped resources

1 to address the energy and economic challenges of our time, fostering economic growth and
2 enhancing living standards for humanity in the coming decades.

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6
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15 16 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

17
18 **Pablo Sanmartín:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology,
19 Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Eduardo F. Fernández:** Writing – review &
20 editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization, Project administration,
21 Funding acquisition. **Antonio García-Loureiro:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation,
22 Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Florencia Almonacid:** Writing – review & editing,
23 Investigation, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

24 25 **Data availability**

26
27 The data that has been used are open to stakeholders among request.

28 29 **Declaration of competing interest**

30
31 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
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33 34 **References**

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